

Genotype to Phenotype: Design of an Extensible Experimental Platform for Characterizing Microbes

A scalable platform for automated microbial phenotyping.

- Growth curve data gathered by laboratory automation.
- Measurements of 1,000 phylogenetically diverse microbes.
- AI-guided experiment selection of 1,000 cultivation conditions for each microbe.

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Additional Acknowledgements:

We acknowledge the following people for their work on science communication:

Olesia Bushkova

Naomi Hagelund

Rachel Sevey

This work was supported by Align to Innovate, which receives philanthropic funding in part from Griffin Catalyst. Align to Innovate is a non-profit research organization operating under open science principles with the goal of improving science research with programmable experiments. Align to Innovate is working to accelerate community-driven science with the use of automated labs to pioneer robust data collection methods and curated, high-fidelity, public biological datasets amenable to machine learning.

Overview

Objective

Currently, there are no predictive models of microbial growth under various conditions that utilize data generated specifically for machine learning applications, and that are collected under consistent experimental conditions. **This project aims to develop an extensible experimental platform and standardized data ontology for collecting phenotypic measurements of microbes grown in various cultivation conditions.** The objective of this dataset is to understand and predict how different environmental conditions interact with microbial genotypes to affect phenotypes such as growth and function, as well as understand and predict gene function of a microbe. This has applications in areas such as climate science and biomanufacturing.

Predictive tasks

The ultimate aim of this dataset is to support the development of predictive models that can bridge the gap between genotype and phenotype in microbiology. This dataset will enable key advancements in this area, allowing us to test specific prediction tasks during the pilot scale and ultimately work toward more generalizable genotype-to-phenotype models. The predictive tasks evaluated during the pilot scale include:

1. Predict the growth of a microbe in a given environment.

- **Input:** Microbial genome and cultivation conditions.
- **Output:** Predicted growth.
- **Description:** This model will allow researchers to input the genomic sequence of a microbe, along with the media conditions, and obtain a prediction of the microbe's growth dynamics in that environment.
- **Example application:** Copper is essential for electrical infrastructure and renewable energy systems. Projections indicate a nearly 4.7 million metric ton deficit by 2030¹. Extracting copper from low grade ores <1% copper content is environmentally and cost inefficient with traditional methods¹. Specialized microbes could be engineered to recover copper from low-grade ores in an environmentally friendly and profitable way. For this to be possible, microbe growth prediction in copper ore substrates would be needed.

2. Optimize media formulation for a specific microbe.

- **Input:** Microbial genome.
- **Output:** Cultivation conditions optimized for growth.
- **Description:** This model will allow researchers to determine the cultivation conditions to use to grow a specific microbe given its genomic sequence.
- **Example application:** Cell culture media impacts cell growth, yield, and product quality in biomanufacturing processes. For example, in the production of a therapeutic DNA vaccine for rheumatoid arthritis using *E. coli*, a media optimization study improved yields by 51.9% compared with the original medium². Designing an improved media formulation tailored to the specific needs of the production strain would enhance growth, maximize product titers, and improve overall process economics.

3. Optimize a microbial genome to process a specific feedstock.

- **Input:** Genome of interest, cultivation conditions, and desired growth rate/yield.
- **Output:** Optimized microbial genome.
- **Description:** This task represents a more advanced level of prediction, where instead of optimizing conditions for an existing microbe, the model suggests genomic modifications to create a microbe optimized for specific production needs.
- **Example application:** Wastewater is a significant environmental and financial burden while at the same time an untapped energy-rich, cheap feedstock source³. Microorganisms engineered to use wastewater as a feedstock integrated in existing wastewater treatment plants would turn waste into value.

Scope

The goal of this proposal is to generate a comprehensive, machine learning-ready dataset comprising growth data for 1,000 culturable microbial strains across 1,000 cultivation conditions, resulting in one million unique experiments. Each strain will be cultured under controlled conditions, and growth measurements will be systematically collected along with a suite of additional phenotypic assays. This dataset aims to provide a deeper understanding of microbial growth dynamics and phenotypes across diverse environmental conditions, ultimately enabling the development of robust predictive models.

This dataset is intended to be a living and growing resource.

Subsequent experiments, beyond those outlined in this proposal, will expand the dataset by incorporating both additional organisms and phenotypic measurements to further enhance the dataset's extensibility and the predictive models it supports.

The project is planned for completion within 24 months, with a budget of \$1M USD. This project will be deemed successful if quantitative data for approximately 1,000 microbes is collected across a minimum of two sites and found to be reproducible.

Definitions

Microbes: free-living, single-celled organisms encompassing bacterial, fungal, and archaeal taxa.

Cultivation Condition: a combination of media components and/or environmental parameters for growing an organism.

Experiment: subjecting a microbe to a cultivation condition in order to produce phenotypes to be measured.

1. Context, Significance, and Impact

Introduction

Microorganisms are ubiquitous, playing vital roles in human health, food production, biogeochemical cycles, disease causation, and offering immense potential for biotechnology applications. They exhibit remarkable diversity, thriving in highly diverse environments that range from the extreme, such as hydrothermal vents, to the more familiar, like soil and the human gut⁴. Despite this vast diversity, only a small fraction of the phylogenetic lineages has been successfully isolated, and our understanding of how environmental conditions influence microbial growth remains limited^{5,6}.

The challenge in understanding microbial growth and activity is compounded by a longstanding focus in microbial culturing efforts to grow microorganisms quickly and easily, rather than understanding their nutritional requirements. Few truly minimal media—those containing the smallest number of distinct nutrients necessary for microbial growth—are available in databases like DSMZ, and there is significant under-sampling of bacterial growth media per organism⁷. Even in BacDive, one of the most comprehensive databases, growth conditions are reported for only ~3-5 media per organism, and growth rates are largely unreported⁸. As a result, significant gaps remain in understanding the specific conditions needed to cultivate many microbial species.

Recent advances in machine learning (ML), combined with high-throughput experimentation, have enabled significant progress in evaluating the impact of environmental factors on microbial growth⁹⁻¹². These advances have shown promise in predicting microbial growth dynamics and improving our ability to design effective growth media, including for previously “unculturable” species. However, existing models are limited by the data on which they are trained, which are often small, focus on well-studied microbes, or are aggregated from disparate sources with varying protocols, which compound to limit their generalizability. To generate robust predictions, ML models require large, biodiverse datasets collected under standardized protocols. Various studies have highlighted the need for such comprehensive datasets to achieve accurate and reliable ML predictions^{9,10}. For instance, a study by Aida et al. found that:

“The variance in the accuracy of repeated model training was too large to reach a reliable prediction. An increase in the abundance of the training data decreased the variance of the model accuracy, demonstrating that a sufficiently large dataset was essentially required to achieve robust ML prediction for the biological experiments”

– Aida et al.¹³

To address these challenges, we propose developing a phenotyping platform that leverages data-driven experimental design and high-throughput experimentation to produce a comprehensive, machine learning-ready dataset. We evaluated commercial

technologies such as Biolog Phenotype Microarrays as potential tools for this effort. However, due to the proprietary nature of key components—specifically the broth formulation and inoculation fluid—these systems are incompatible with Align’s commitment to open, reproducible science.

This platform will focus on understanding and predicting how environmental conditions impact microbial phenotypes, such as growth and function. The dataset will include phenotypic data for 1,000 phylogenetically diverse microbial strains across 1,000 cultivation conditions, resulting in one million unique experiments.

Our platform will utilize BacterAI, a reinforcement learning agent that designs automated condition variation experiments to maximize the knowledge base¹¹. In collaboration with strain repositories (e.g., ATCC, DTU), strains will be carefully selected to maximize biodiversity, ensuring the dataset captures the broadest possible range of microbial life.

This dataset will provide a valuable resource for understanding microbial growth dynamics across diverse environmental conditions and will enable the development of robust predictive models. We predict that this dataset will enable a wide range of prediction tasks, such as predicting microbial growth in a given environment, optimizing media formulations for a particular microbe, and ultimately designing microbial genomes tailored to process specific feedstocks. We envision this resource will enable a reliable genotype-to-phenotype predictive model that will advance both basic and applied microbial research.

Example Applications

This dataset will enable predictive tasks that have a wide range of applications across fields such as agriculture, climate science, and biomanufacturing. Beyond industrial applications, these models will also advance basic science by providing deeper insights into fundamental microbial growth patterns and metabolic processes. Example applications include:

Climate, Agriculture & Sustainability

The predictive models described above can play a critical role in advancing environmental applications directly supporting the objectives outlined in the United States’ “*Bold Goals for U.S. Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing*”¹⁴. For instance, these models can advance biomining processes by deepening our understanding of microbial interactions with metals and metal-bearing ores, leading to more efficient resource extraction¹⁵. In agriculture, predictive models can be used to optimize microbial activity to reduce methane emissions or for soil carbon restoration¹⁶, supporting climate goals¹⁷. Models can also be used to engineer microbes capable of converting bio-based feedstocks into sustainable polymers that can replace traditional plastics, and to upcycle plastic waste into biofuels, advancing both environmental sustainability and energy innovation. These models may also be used to bioprospect for environmental genomes able to utilize diverse carbon sources, improving predictions of the fate of carbon in soil and aquatic systems as well as biotechnological applications targeting uti-

lization of bio-based feedstocks. These models could also be used to determine which organisms could have potential for plant growth promotion or plant pathogen control.

Bio manufacturing

In the bio manufacturing industry, predictive models will provide a powerful tool for identifying optimal media conditions that support microbial growth and insights into strain performance in novel environments, thereby unlocking new applications. These models can predict the genetic modifications required for microbes to efficiently process specific feedstocks, optimizing fermentation processes by fine-tuning conditions to enhance yields, reduce byproducts, improve product quality, and reduce production costs^{18,19}. The models enabled by this dataset will accelerate R&D by guiding the engineering of microbes with desired traits, resulting in faster strain development and advancing the objectives outlined in the “*Bold Goals for U.S. Biotechnology and Bio manufacturing*”¹⁴. These models will also facilitate bio manufacturing in low-resource environments, such as space missions or developing countries, and enable the use of waste streams as sustainable feedstocks²⁰.

Basic Science

Our predictive models will advance basic science by addressing one of the field’s greatest challenges: identifying optimal culture conditions for previously “unculturable” microorganisms, potentially enabling a deeper understanding of valuable microorganisms from environmental sources. Additionally, models from this dataset are expected to uncover new environments where known organisms can thrive and show phenotype patterns for gene/gene clusters of unknown function. This will be a key focus of collaboration with the broader scientific community. We will work with the community to develop and benchmark such models as well as experimentally validate predictions during this project.

What are the Existing Microbial Conditions Datasets?

Examples of existing datasets in this space are summarized in [Supplemental Table 1](#). To our knowledge, current datasets are often limited in scope, either due to their small size or narrow

focus, or are aggregations of existing data from various sources and collected under inconsistent experimental conditions. For example, **MediaDive**, the world’s first cultivation media database, relates microbial strains to media recipes in which growth has been reported. Although MediaDive is an important resource that standardizes media recipes and nomenclature, the data it contains is manually curated from a variety of sources, including internal DSMZ files, existing publications, and other assorted documents²¹. Most strains are only noted with ~3-5 media. Cultivation methods and data collection protocols may differ between various reported growths for a single strain. The major limitation is, though, that no negative growth datasets are reported, making it nearly impossible to use these data for predictive modeling. Additional phenotypic data are hosted in the related **BacDive** database. Similarly, BacDive, one of the most comprehensive resources available to date, aggregates data from both internal DSMZ sources, other culture collections and scientific literature, supplemented by AI-derived phenotypic predictions based on genome-phenome associations⁸. Data represented in both BacDive and MediaDive are not collected using a single collection strategy. Such datasets often exhibit significant noise due to variations in how the phenotypes are defined and obtained, limiting their applicability in machine learning²². Other databases, such as **MediaDB** and **KOMODO**, are also manually curated from various sources, focused primarily on model organisms, and are no longer accessible^{7,23}. **Aida et al.** presented one of the closest datasets to the one we propose, generating 12,828 growth curves for a single strain of *E. coli* across 966 media combinations¹³.

Our proposed work differs from existing datasets by focusing our effort on large-scale data collection for 1,000 microbes across 1,000 conditions tested using the same protocols with various phenotypic measurements. The resulting dataset will be 1,000 times larger than that of Aida et al. and cover far more genotypic diversity. During the process development stage, we will concentrate on well-studied and industrially relevant microbes with a focus on bio manufacturing, agriculture, and food/health applications. Once our platform is established, we will expand to include a broader range of microbial species that maximize the biodiversity represented in the dataset.

Building a standardized dataset of growth of microbial strains across various conditions in a consistent experimental setting would be of great value to develop impactful predictive models of microbial growth.

Figure 2: Summary of existing datasets in microbial growth. Citations can be found in [Supplemental Table 1](#).

2. Experimental Design

2.1. Phased Approach

In order to optimize methods and perform intermediate analysis of predictive models before full-scale experimentation, the dataset is divided into the three stages below:

- 1. Process development:** A small-scale dataset with 20 organisms, including a control, used to test and refine experimental methods before full-scale deployment. Each organism will be tested in 1,000 conditions yielding a total of 20,000 data points.
- 2. Pilot scale:** A mid-scale dataset involving 230 organisms cultivated in 1,000 different conditions used for intermediate ML analysis. This stage will yield 230,000 data points.
- 3. Full-scale experiments:** Testing an additional 750 organisms across 1,000 conditions to increase the biodiversity of the dataset, generating 750,000 data points.

2.2. Organism Selection Strategy

As part of the initial scope of this proposal, we plan to study the growth of 1,000 phylogenetically diverse microbes in 1,000 cultivation conditions resulting in one million unique experiments. Microbes in this context are defined as unique species' genomes and their variants, encompassing bacterial, fungal, and archaeal taxa.

All strains will be sourced from established culture collections, such as ATCC, or through community donations. Strains from culture collections will have complete genome sequences

and received aliquots will be verified by the culture collection using 16S rRNA gene sequencing for bacteria and archaea or ITS sequencing for fungi prior to shipment. As part of this proposal, 16S/ITS sequencing will be collected for samples post the onboarding stage and before condition variation to confirm that the intended samples are growing under the basic environmental conditions and media chosen during the onboarding stage.

Organisms will be selected to maximize the biodiversity represented in the final dataset. We will begin with well-studied organisms and expand the sampling across diverse taxonomic clades. This will include clusters of similar organisms to investigate within-group variation. The strategies for each phase of methods development, pilot testing, and full-scale experiments are detailed in the subsequent sections. However, all organisms must meet the criteria outlined below to be included in the study:

- Be culturable in at least one liquid media and compatible with plate-based growth (show reproducible growth).
- Be categorized as BSL1 or BSL2.
- Not be obligate photoautotrophs.
- Doubling time must be between 15 minutes and 24 hours.
- Must grow at temperatures between 25°C and 45°C.

New methods and equipment would be required to support a broader variety of microbes. Future iterations of the dataset may expand beyond these initial restrictions.

2.3. Seed Train Strategy

Strains will be sourced from ATCC or another culture collection, with strain identity verified through 16S rRNA sequencing for bacteria or ITS sequencing for fungi, ensuring they are free from contamination.

Each culture from the supplier will be revived from a frozen or freeze-dried stock according to the supplier's instructions. Each day, a technician will thaw (or resuspend) a batch of cultures, each of which will be streaked onto an agar plate and used to inoculate a 24 well plate. Contamination will be monitored through 16S rRNA/ITS sequencing, and if any contamination is detected, we will transition to using single tubes. Growth curves

for each plate will be collected and a glycerol freezer stock will be made from wells that grow. Glycerol stocks will be adjusted to a cell number so all experiments can be compared. The agar plate will be imaged and stored. This is the most human-intensive part of the process, as each culture will be treated according to the supplier's recommendations.

Once the glycerol stock is in the freezer, it will be tracked by a database developed by the Jensen Lab. This means that any starter culture (overnights, etc.) will be tracked in the database. For this project we prefer to use 24 or 11 well plates rather than culture tubes for overnights to simplify tracking and growth monitoring.

2.4. Condition Variation Strategy

2.4.1. Profiling Stages

We will profile the growth of every microbe in 1,000 conditions that span combinations of different environments, base growth media, and media alterations. We will investigate 147 different media factors with our automated phenotyping platform (Table 1).

Category	Type	Factors
Environments	Atmosphere	2 (5% CO ₂ or anaerobic (80% N ₂ , 15% CO ₂ , 5% H ₂))
	Temperature	4 (spanning 25°C–42°C)
	Shaking	2 (shaking or non-shaking)
Base Media Type	Undefined Rich Media (ex. LB, BHI)	7
	Semi-Defined Media (ex. contains yeast extract but otherwise defined)	2
	Defined Media	2
Media Additions, Substitutions, and Removals	Carbon Sources	22
	Amino Acids	20
	Other Nitrogen/Phosphorus/Sulfur Sources	9
	Vitamin Cofactors	11
	Nucleobases	5
	Metals and Salts	8
	Antimicrobials & Anti-fungals*	50
pH	3 (pH 5.0, 7.0, 9.0)	
Total Factors		147

*Tested at clinically relevant concentrations as reported in the literature.

Table 1: We will phenotype every microbe in combinations of up to 149 different factors. A full list of base media types and chemicals is available in [Supplemental Table 2](#).

Our panel of factors will allow researchers to map how microbes respond to a vast array of environments; however, not all environments will be relevant or informative to test. Our experimental approach assumes no prior knowledge about a microbe's growth capabilities, so it is difficult to select which 1,000

conditions to test for every microbe *a priori*. Instead, we will use an adaptive approach to select informative experiments. Each microbe will be profiled in the three stages, and the results of each stage will be used to plan subsequent experiments:

Figure 5: Profiling stages for each organism.

1. Strain onboarding screen (44 runs)

The first stage is designed to uncover the basic growth requirements of the microbes. We will culture each microbe (using the same glycerol stock inoculum) in a set of 11 different base media in four different environments (aerobic or anaerobic and 25°C or 37°C). The 11 media used will consist of undefined, semi-defined, or defined media that we believe support the growth of a large group of microbes. The goal is to limit the number of “working media” we need to prepare every day for screening.

Only the media and environments that the microbe grows in will be considered in subsequent stages. For example, if a microbe only grows in anaerobic conditions, we will do all future experiments in anaerobic conditions. Any microbes that do not grow reproducibly in the working media will be saved for a special batch in the full phase where we can decide if they are worth additional effort.

In this stage, a rough estimate for how quickly the organisms grow will be obtained and used to group the organisms by growth rate/the number of data needed for a growth experiment for subsequent stages.

2. Human-designed screens

Stage two profiles the growth of each microbe in more complex environments and media. This stage consists of two screens performed in parallel.

a. Environment screen (up to 32 runs)

We will screen each microbe in combinations of four temperatures (25°C, 30°C, 37°C, 42°C), two shaking conditions (+/-), two atmospheres (+/- oxygen), and two base media. **At most, each microbe will be screened in $4 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 = 32$ conditions.** We will not vary the atmosphere for strict anaerobes or aerobes (as determined in the strain onboarding screen). The base media will vary from strain to strain, but we will select the two most robust media (supports growth in the most conditions) identified in the strain onboarding screen.

b. Media alteration screen (up to 1,440 runs (up to 16 90-run plates))

The bulk of the human-designed runs profile growth in different media. We will select 90 conditions (one plate) to test at a time using a three-step sampling strategy (Fig. 5):

- 1. Select atmosphere:** All experiments will be grown at one temperature in either aerobic or anaerobic conditions, depending on which atmospheres support growth in the microbe.
- 2. Select base media:** We will identify up to three screening media for each microbe (one undefined, one semi-defined, and one defined) and choose one media for the set of runs.
- 3. Select alteration panel:** There will be eight different sets of 90 media alterations spanning the list of media components outlined in Table 1. The eight sets will be grown in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions if both support the growth of the organism (16 plates total). Each set will generally vary a group of components (i.e. stressors or carbon sources) and will consider single and low-level combinatorial perturbations. We will select one of these sets to run on each plate. The available sets are conditional on the selected base media. For instance, undefined media will be more restrictive than defined media.

Some organisms will be screened more heavily than others. **At a maximum, each organism will be screened in 2 atmospheres \times 8 condition panels \times 90 runs = 1440 runs.** Most organisms will be screened with fewer runs. Strict anaerobes and aerobes will receive at most 720 runs, and organisms that only grow in defined or semi-defined media will only be screened in a subset of the alteration panels. On average, each organism will be screened in approximately 1,000 conditions as part of the project, with the total number of experiments across all organisms being capped at 1 million.

3. Model-guided screen (remaining runs up to 1,000)

In the final stage, BacterAI, a reinforcement learning agent, will design combinatorial experiments and build a predictive model of each microbe's growth¹¹. We will allow BacterAI to use the remaining run budget to investigate higher-order factor interactions in the growth conditions tested in stage two. In cases where we approach the 1,440-run maximum for an organism, additional experiments will be assigned to BacterAI to ensure it learns and contributes valuable data for these organisms.

The process for selecting each day's experiments is as follows:

1. All the experiments for the phase (process development, pilot, or full) are entered into a run queue.
2. The technician selects what microbes are available that day, ensuring that any strains that will be present on the same plate have similar growth rates, and inputs the environments that will be used. Based on the number of

liquid handlers used, the scheduler identifies how many plates can be processed that day.

3. The plates are filled with runs from the run queue and the liquid handling is planned, compiled, and added in the database. Note that assays are randomized onto the plates; there is no single plate layout used. This strategy 1.) avoids systematic plate effects during the entire project, and 2.) avoids waste and re-work that occurs when a single incubator goes down, a reagent runs out, or the pre-screen culture (overnight) does not grow.
4. Dispensing begins, followed by inoculation, initial OD reading, and incubation.
5. The plates are removed from incubation for every data collection and OD readings. In step 2, the strains were chosen to have similar growth rates, so the OD readings continue for 1+ days depending on the growth rate.

2.4.2. Standard Media Selection

The standard media will be determined during experimentation and may vary between microbial groups, such as bacteria and fungi. Potential media options are listed below. We may also include growth media used by the culture collection to propagate the strains.

Bacteria

- Nutrient Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 3)
- Tryptic Soy Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 18)
- Yeast Malt Extract Medium (e.g., ATCC Medium 0196)
- Brain Heart Infusion Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 44)
- Tryptic Soy Medium with 5% Defibrinated Sheep Blood (e.g., ATCC Medium 0260)
- Marine Medium 2216 (e.g., ATCC Medium 0002)
- Lowenstein-Jensen Medium (e.g., ATCC Medium 90)
- Todd-Hewitt Broth
- Luria-Bertani Broth
- M9 Minimal Broth
- Modified Gifu Anaerobic Broth (mGAM)
- 7H9 Broth (Mycobacteria)
- NLDM²⁴
- Clostridial Medium (e.g., ATCC 2107)

Mycology

Yeast

- YEPD or Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose (e.g., ATCC Medium 2241)
- SD Minimal Media

Filamentous Fungi

- Potato Dextrose Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 336)
- YM Medium Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 200)
- Sabouraud Dextrose Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 28)
- Malt Extract Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 325)
- V-8 Juice Broth (e.g., ATCC Medium 0343)

3. Process Development

3.1. Stage Overview

During process development, we will test our protocols and methods with well-studied organisms prior to scaling up and determine the appropriate stage gates/QC pipeline for this project. In this stage, we will select a set of 11 standard media that we will use for 1.) bringing strains into the screening lab (onboarding), 2.) growing pre-cultures before screening, and 3.) screening environments and stressors (anaerobic environments, antimicrobials, low pH).

Strains for this stage will be selected from the culture collection that are known to grow in the 11 standard media. This will be verified when the strain arrives at the screening lab. During

2.5. Data Collection

Prior to condition variation experiments:

- **Whole genome sequencing.** Performed if sequencing data is not available from the strain provider.
- **16S rRNA (Bacteria) or ITS (Fungi) sequencing.** Performed on strains post onboarding and prior to human and model-designed screens. Samples may also be collected throughout the platform to spot-check for contamination.
Note: 16S/ITS sequencing will also be performed on each organism by the culture collection prior to shipping.

Data collection from condition variation experiments:

- **OD600 UV-Vis spectroscopy.** Measurements will be collected in a BioTek Epoch 2, Cytation 5, or Cytation 10 multimodal plate reader with monochromator emitters. Data will be collected at multiple timepoints throughout condition variation experiments to generate complete growth curves. Plates will be briefly agitated with linear/orbital shaking in the reader before the timepoint to disaggregate cells and provide a more reliable absorbance measurement.
- **Phase contrast microscopy and confocal microscopy (endpoint, once per organism in a specified condition).** Performed at 60x using a BioTek Cytation 10 automated imaging plate reader with laser autofocus.
- **pH endpoint.** Evaluated during methods development for feasibility. Measured using a colorimetric method.

initial media screening, microbes will still be tested in all 11 standard media in case the microbe grows better in a different media. (For example, the standard rich media used in the field for some streptococci differs from the ATCC culture conditions for the microbe, although the ATCC media supports growth.)

During this stage, we will refine three workflows:

1. **Onboarding strains.** Strains will arrive at the site either frozen or freeze-dried, possibly in ampules. Strains will arrive from a culture collection that has identified at least one media/environment in which the strain grows. The strain will be plated, a liquid culture will be inoculated, and a glycerol stock will be made after growth. Images of the plates and growth kinetics will be recorded.

2. Initial media screening. Each strain will be tested in a standard set of ~11 base media (both defined and undefined) in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. These results will inform a decision tree for future experiments. For example, testing antibiotic sensitivity could be done in the media with the highest growth rate.

3. Condition screening. Using the data from the initial screen, conditions will be varied in 96 well plates in a combination of human and ML-designed conditions. ML conditions will be selected by Bayesian optimization models for each strain based on the initial and human-designed screening. ML conditions will be complex, i.e. with multiple factors varied simultaneously in order to maximize the information gained.

This stage will also be used to evaluate:

1. Lot-to-lot media variation. Media will be prepared by the partner lab using its standard constituents and also sourced from Teknova. Two labs will independently test the growth of a small subset of strains in both media types, with results compared to assess variability arising from media differences. If the Teknova-sourced media yields more reproducible growth across labs, it will be selected for use throughout the remainder of the project.

2. Use of oxyrase for simulating anaerobic conditions. Incorporating oxyrase into the media provides a flexible way to simulate anaerobic environments, allowing more experimental factors to be screened simultaneously. Oxyrase is an oxygen-fixing enzyme that removes dissolved oxygen from liquid creating an anaerobic environment within each well, even when the plate is incubated under aerobic conditions²⁵. To evaluate its effectiveness, identical plates will be grown under three conditions: (1) anaerobic chambers, (2) aerobic conditions, and (3) aerobic conditions with oxyrase in the media. The results from this test will guide the experimental design choices in the pilot and full-scale experiments.

3. Feasibility of a colorimetric pH assay for post-growth endpoint pH measurements. The method described by Engevik et al. will be evaluated for integration into the platform²⁶. This evaluation will include pre-testing across the media used in this study to ensure compatibility and establishing required controls, such as non-dyed controls, to detect potential interference in the phenol red readout.

3.2. Organisms

The organisms listed below will be used in the process development stage to test protocols and assays prior to the pilot-scale run. *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, or *S. cerevisiae* will be used as positive controls in each experimental batch. Refer to [Section 7](#) for more details on the control strategy used for this dataset. All microbial strains used during process development will be obtained from ATCC, and therefore will have genome sequences and can be grown in a known medium and environment.

The selection of the process development organisms was based on the following criteria:

- Commonly used in industry or academia (data available).
- Grow quickly in liquid culture.
- Industrially relevant.
- Likely to grow in the 11 standard media selected.

3.3. Advancement Criteria

To advance from the process development stage to the pilot stage, the following criteria must be met:

Step 1: Controls should produce expected and consistent outcomes.

Step 2: A subset of experimental results must demonstrate reproducibility across two independent sites (N=2). Strain growth patterns, including key metrics like growth rates and phenotypic outputs, must show consistent and reliable results across both sites, with minimal acceptable variation.

Organisms	Applications	Supplier/Strain Information	Biosafety (ATCC)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> K-12	Internal Standards	ATCC® 10798™	BSL1
<i>Escherichia coli</i> BL21	Internal Standards	ATCC® BAA-1025™	BSL1
<i>Escherichia coli</i> W3110	Internal Standards	ATCC® 27325™	BSL1
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Marburg	Production	ATCC® 6051™	BSL1
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	Production	ATCC® 14580™	BSL1
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Production	ATCC® 14579™	BSL1
<i>Vibrio natriegens</i>	Like <i>E. Coli</i> , but Faster	ATCC® 14048™	BSL1
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> KT2440	Often Used for Bioremediation	ATCC® 47054™	BSL1
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> BCY123	Model Fungi	ATCC® MYA-5007™	BSL1
<i>Rhodotorula toruloides</i> IIP30	Fungi	ATCC® 204091™	BSL1
<i>Yarrowia lipolytica</i> PO1f <i>Industrial Biomanufacturing</i>	Fermentation, Good Production Workhorse	ATCC® MYA-2613™	BSL1
<i>Komagataella pastoris</i> NRRL Y-11430 (aka <i>Pichia pastoris</i>) <i>Industrial Biomanufacturing</i> <i>Food+Health</i>	Protein Expression + Secretion	ATCC® 76273™	BSL1
<i>Corynebacterium glutamicum</i> 534 <i>Industrial Biomanufacturing</i> <i>Food+Health</i>	Large-Scale Production of Amino Acids	ATCC® 13032™	BSL1
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> NCFM Scav <i>Food+Health</i>	Food, Fermentation Products	ATCC® 4356™	BSL1
<i>Veillonella parvula</i> <i>Food+Health</i>	Strictly Anaerobic. Part of the Oral Flora	ATCC® 10790™	BSL1
<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i> LMD-9 <i>Food+Health</i>	Dairy Fermentation	ATCC® BAA-491™	BSL1
<i>Bifidobacterium bifidum</i> <i>Food+Health</i>	Probiotics	ATCC® 700541™	BSL1
<i>Agrobacterium tumefaciens</i> C58 <i>Agriculture</i>	Used for Plant Delivery Vector	ATCC® 33970™	BSL1
<i>Rhizobium leguminosarum</i> 3D1k2 <i>Agriculture</i>	Nitrogen Fixation in Plants	ATCC® 14479™	BSL1
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> NCTC 10038 <i>Agriculture</i>	Controls Plant Pathogens	ATCC® 13525™	BSL1

Table 2: Development & control organisms.

4. Pilot Scale

4.1. Stage Overview

Upon successful completion of the process development stage, an additional 250 organisms will be tested in a pilot-scale experiment. This stage is designed to build on previous findings by applying the developed methods to a larger set of samples. The data collected during this phase will be used for initial machine learning (ML) model testing and evaluation, allowing for further refinement of methods if necessary for model performance before proceeding to full-scale experiments.

4.2. Organisms

In this stage, a **rational, human-curated** selection strategy will be used to select 250 organisms using power-law sampling to select clusters of similar organisms to study within-group variation, and outliers from diverse groups that are likely to grow in the standard set of ~11 base media chosen during the process development stage. A literature search will be implemented to confirm whether the species chosen have reported growth in any of the standard media prior to starting experimentation.

The strains will be onboarded in the known media from the cul-

ture collection but tested in the 11 standard media. Strains that grow in at least one standard medium will be used in the pilot phase. Any species selected for characterization that do not grow in the standard set of media used and require a unique media will be collected in a “difficult” group. This group will be reserved for full-scale experiments and assessed for inclusion in the dataset based on time and budget.

4.3. Advancement Criteria

To transition from the pilot phase to full-scale deployment, the same criteria as in the process development phase must be satisfied, with the addition of **Step 3** below, to ensure scalability, reproducibility, and predictive capability of the experimental process and dataset.

Step 3: An intermediate analysis of ML models trained on the pilot dataset must demonstrate the ability to make predictions based on the collected data. This analysis should confirm the data’s suitability for ML-driven predictions with reasonable belief that expanding the dataset will further enhance model performance.

5. Full scale

5.1. Stage Overview

Following the successful completion of the pilot-scale phase, the full-scale experiments will expand the testing to an additional 750 organisms. The primary goal of this stage is to enrich the biodiversity represented in the dataset and provide a more comprehensive training set for machine learning (ML) models. Similar to the previous phases, results will undergo rigorous analysis to ensure that controls perform as expected and that reproducibility is confirmed across two independent sites.

5.2. Organisms

During full-scale experiments, the remaining 750 organisms will be selected to maximize the biodiversity of strains represented in the dataset. To do this, organisms will be selected using one of the selection strategies below:

Community vote

In this subpool, the broader scientific community will participate in voting to select organisms to include in the dataset. Researchers can vote on “difficult” organisms identified in the pilot scale as well as nominate untested organisms from the ATCC collection they believe are important to include. This collaborative approach aims to gather input from the scientific community and ensure that the dataset includes organisms that are relevant to current research. Microbes from the “difficult” group not screened will be published alongside the dataset with all attempts to grow them in standard media as they represent a challenge group that can be used to test the ML models or to spur the discovery of new auxotrophies.

In an effort to further engage the community in the dataset and increase the diversity of organisms, we will also be opening this subpool to include isolates donated from the broader scientific community. Any cultures donated must satisfy the criteria listed in [Section 2.2](#), and have at least one known culture condition before entering the screening lab. Bioprospecting groups will need to isolate strains that can be cultured in the lab from environmental samples prior to donating culture. Any organisms not previously sequenced will also be sent for whole genome sequencing (WGS).

Community donations will be accepted starting in late 2025, with testing scheduled for 2026. If community engagement falls short of expectations, we will use the sampling algorithm described below to select the remaining organisms from the ATCC collection maximizing biodiversity.

Structured search

This strategy utilizes algorithms to perform a structured and systematic search of the ATCC genome database to identify strains that can maximally increase the biodiversity represented in the dataset. An algorithm will be developed to utilize a “genomic distance” measure, selecting strains that introduce valuable diversity by targeting those genetically distant from previously chosen strains or containing large amounts of novel DNA not yet present in the collection. Any algorithms and/or analyses developed as part of this proposal will be made publicly available. All microbes onboarded during this phase will be screened in the 11 standard media, and, if they grow, cultured in a standard medium whenever possible.

Figure 8: Organism Selection Strategy.

6. Quality Control Plan

All experiments for this project will be done in standard 96-well plates and follow the quality control plan outlined below. This will be refined further during the process development stage. Our platform includes a set of control experiments on every plate to autonomously monitor and correct for three types of errors:

- 1. Batch variation in strain growth:** Experiments on each strain will be done in batches, so a particular strain may appear on multiple plates over multiple days during the project. Each plate containing experiments for a particular strain will include a set of positive growth control experiments for that strain. The growth medium for the control will be the base media identified during strain onboarding that yields the most consistent growth. We will monitor batch controls for each strain using Shewhart control charts to detect deviations from expected growth patterns.
- 2. Contamination and Dispensing Errors:** While automation scales up microbial phenotyping research, it can make hardware errors and contamination difficult to detect. In addition to the positive controls discussed in the previous section, our platform includes a set of negative control growth experiments on every plate. Each negative control (or blank) will be an un-inoculated well containing the same media used for the positive controls. We will monitor the growth of negative controls for possible contamination or liquid handler issues. Contamination will also be carefully monitored during method development using 16S rRNA/ITS sequencing or Rapid Microbial ID. Samples will be collected throughout the platform to verify that the platform design does not pose a significant contamination issue.
- 3. Spatial variation in microwell plates:** An experiment's location in a microwell plate can affect its measured growth. For example, after incubation, media evaporation is more pronounced at the edges of the plate than at the center. Evaporation decreases the height of the liquid column in wells, so it skews measurements made by absorbance plate readers. We place controls using a semi-random space-filling design such that controls are spread out in different regions of the plate. We will use the controls to monitor and correct for plate spatial effects.

Our platform places experiments and controls with custom arraying software. **Each plate will include a set of six positive and six negative controls.** The controls will be allocated in proportion to the number of wells each strain occupies. In the example in Fig. 8, Strain A (green) receives four purple positive controls and four black negative controls. Strain B (orange) receives the remaining controls.

Figure 9: Two strains are present on this plate, represented as green and orange wells. Positive (blue) and negative (black) controls are placed to detect biological and technical variation.

In addition to the control experiments, each liquid handler in the lab will be tested daily using a dye-based pipetting assay. We will monitor the performance of the liquid handlers using Shewhart control charts and will repair or recalibrate them when issues are detected.

A process log for the entire system will track any observations made by the technicians or automation engineers. Additionally, every movement, exposure, and source transfer will be stored in a database developed by the Jensen Lab allowing post hoc quality control by correlating non-conforming results with changes in reagents, delays in dispensing, or other events. The goal is to log every part of every experiment, ensuring the quality control continues long after the data are released.

7. N=2 Strategy

To ensure the robustness, scalability, and repeatability of the dataset, experiments will be carried out at two or more facilities. During each phase, a subset of organisms tested at Site 1 will be re-evaluated under a subset of conditions at Site 2 to ensure the reproducibility of the methods. Results from both sites must be reproducible to advance to the next phase.

8. Data Analysis and Machine Learning Evaluation

8.1. Data Analysis

Before model training, every well will be normalized twice by two sets of controls. The first, the *plate controls*, are 12 wells randomly placed on each 96 well plate containing six wells where the organism grows and six wells where it doesn't. The positive and negative controls will be selected from the initial screen of 11 media. (If an organism grows in all 11 initial media, DI water will be used for blanks.) The plate control normalizes each organism's growth across **conditions** to a set of reference conditions with robust growth.

The second normalization uses *batch controls*, which is a plate containing a control organism with robust growth (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. cerevisiae*, etc.). The batch control plates will be compared to batch controls from different days to calculate the day's scaling factor. This factor will be applied to all experiments in the day's batch to ensure consistency across **organisms**.

In the end, all growth data will be reported as four values: raw OD, plate normalized (each organism's growth relative to a control media), batch normalized (each organism's growth relative to a control media, but adjusted for day-to-day-variation), and control organism normalized (each organism's growth relative to, say, growth of *E. coli* K12).

8.2. Data & Metadata Schema

The proposed data schema is illustrated in Fig. 11 and will undergo refinement during method development to align with standard database schema recommendations and encompass all relevant semantic and linked data. Our goal is to incorporate as much metadata as possible, including those relevant to automated instrument instructions. During method development, appropriate ontologies will be selected to effectively suit the specific data and metadata, ensuring they are suitable for logical reasoning in machine learning applications. Data will be semantically annotated using standardized methods and stored in a unified format.

Regardless of the ontology chosen, all the "raw" data will be stored in the Jensen lab's CHESS database format, which records every movement, liquid transfer, plate reading, and environmental reading, for both humans and robots in the lab (unpublished work, Benjamin David, University of Michigan). This system contains enough data to recreate the entire experimental campaign *in silico*. Thus, we can change the schema later based on the needs of the ML engineers and re-extract the relevant information. The final ontology will evolve with the project without worry that an important piece of metadata wasn't collected at runtime.

Figure 11: Data schema. An expanded version of the diagram is available [here](#).

8.3. Data Storage

Data will be made available in an Align-hosted database accessible to the public through a REST API. For longevity and redundancy of data, snapshots of this database at certain time points (e.g., for the initial data set, or for large data increases) will be duplicated to a third-party repository (e.g., BacDive⁸, Nature Scientific Data²⁷ or Zenodo).

8.4. Analysis Strategy for Predictive Modeling of Pilot Data

8.4.1. Proposed Predictive Model Tasks & Evaluation

The data collected from this proposal can be used to develop models for a variety of predictive tasks. Below, we outline the tasks we anticipate will be successful in making these predictions, along with our testing strategy. The primary aim of this work is not to establish new predictive models in biology, but to demonstrate that this dataset enables others to pursue such approaches. We intend to provide a foundation for the research community to test and refine these models further. This dataset will also be used to collaborate with researchers who are already developing relevant models in the community.

Predictive models require evaluation to determine if sparsity in the data or nuisance variables is affecting prediction accuracy. The standard model evaluation metrics (accuracy (MSE or cross entropy), ROC, etc.) will be used to assess the training process. Align will select appropriate metrics for each of the tasks identified and provide a framework that supports the research community in testing and refining their predictive models. Metrics will rely only on the model prediction task and phenotype data, such that they can be applied to diverse predictive modeling approaches.

Task 1: Predict the growth of a microbe in a given environment.

The first task predicts if a microbe (represented by a feature vector or model embedding from its genome) will grow in an environment (represented as a feature vector of the media/environmental factors). The output of the model is either a classifier (grow/no grow), regression task on some parameter from the growth curve collection from the experiment (lag time, max growth rate, max OD, etc.), or the growth curve itself. For grow/no grow data, a growth threshold will need to be calculated for each organism or each environment. Calculating by organism may be preferable, as some of the AI-generated conditions may only be tested for one strain. Either way, the threshold may be set by separating all growth data (max OD) into two groups by minimizing the inter-group variance (e.g., by Otsu's method²⁸).

Several downstream applications of this model are relevant to test the predictive capabilities and generalizability of the ML models trained on this dataset:

1. Bioprospecting of environmental microbial genomes for desired growth conditions. E.g., predict growth on carbon sources or growth conditions of interest for all complete or near-complete environmental microbial genomes obtained via metagenomic assembly or single-cell sequencing. This task is relevant to applications in wastewater or carbon remediation, biomaterials development, and biofuels.
2. Predict functional capabilities of environmental microbial genomes under *in situ* or *in silico* conditions. E.g., predict the ability of different (cultured or uncultured) genomes within an assembled metagenome or from a single-cell sequencing sample to grow on different carbon sources as a sole carbon source.

Task 2: Optimize media formulation for a specific microbe.

Other users are interested in optimizing a media for a specific microbe. This task requires selecting a scalar-valued objective over all possible media that is to be optimized, for example, maximum growth rate, maximum yield per C-mol, or minimum lag time. Such a task would require a regression model from Task 1 and is accomplished by fixing the genome of the organism and searching *in silico* for a media that extremizes the objective.

Task 3: Optimize a microbial genome to process a specific feedstock.

We anticipate this to be the most challenging and ambitious predictive task. Users may want to optimize for a genome that processes a specific feedstock. For this task to be accomplished using this project's data, the processing would need to be growth coupled – secondary breakdown of a feedstock that does not produce biomass would require data about the metabolic outputs of microbes in environments. To accomplish the task, users would fix the environment with the feedstock and then search *in silico* for genomic perturbations that optimize the growth of a regression model from Task 1. Note that the search for genomes may be highly constrained. For example, users may want to limit the search to genomes that can be produced by a fixed number of gene deletions/additions to an existing genome. In other cases, users may want freedom to design a complete genome from scratch or users may want to design an algorithm to select combinations of genes or operons from a database of disparate genomes into a single new bioengineered organism.

8.4.2. Model Metadata

All models will share certain core metadata, while some will include additional, specific metadata. The guiding philosophy of this proposal is to capture and report all available metadata for all models, using a consistent structure. We will develop an infrastructure to capture all relevant metadata and the protocols used for analysis in a manner that allows extensibility and machine readability.

All model architectures, parameters, training time (including hardware specifications), and performance (accuracy and precision) will be released alongside the training code. The data used for each training run, including the test/train splits, will also be recorded and released. For regression models, the mean square error and/or cross entropy loss curves will be recorded.

8.4.3. Proposed Methods for Predictive Model Validation

Beyond training, the most important validation of a model is its ability to predict new results. We believe there are two natural “tests” for growth models:

1. **Predict a new environment for a previously cultured organism.** For example, the Gram-positive model organism *Bacillus subtilis* was long believed to be a strict aerobe before conditions supporting anaerobic growth were discovered in 1997²⁹. Similarly, the growth data could be used to identify surprising new growth conditions for established organisms.
2. **Predict growth media for “unculturable” organisms.** The vast majority of the microbes in any given environmental sample have not been cultured individually, a phenomenon known as “The Great Plate Count Anomaly”³⁰. A second goal would be to predict the culture conditions for an organism that has been identified through a genome sequence from a metagenome but has not been grown individually. Model performance could be evaluated as a function of the genetic distance (ANI) between the new organism and the training data (either closest match or average distance) to get an idea of how well the models can extrapolate to new organisms.

We will validate using both *in silico* and experimental approaches:

- ***In Silico* validation.** A subset of the dataset will be held out as a final test set, enabling researchers to benchmark their models on unseen data. Additionally, we propose organizing modeling tournaments to predict growth outcomes for either the holdout set or a newly screened set of organisms, fostering a collaborative and competitive environment to refine prediction strategies.
- **Experimental validation.** The predictions outlined above could be tested experimentally by culturing known organisms in new media (#1) or growing a metagenomic sample in the predicted growth media to isolate a previously unculturable species (#2).

9. Dataset Expansion

Figure 12: Dataset expansion dimensions.

9.1. Additional Organisms

The dataset can be expanded by testing additional diverse organisms. This could include exploring underrepresented taxonomic groups, sourcing samples from diverse ecological niches, or expanding beyond the selection criteria outlined in [Section 2.2](#). Additionally, once the platform is established, Align to Innovate may accept sample submissions from scientists worldwide and fund their analysis. This data will be added to the dataset from this proposal after an embargo period to allow researchers time to file provisional patents or publish papers on resulting data. This will allow the dataset to grow over time and include an increasingly representative collection of microbial life.

There is also an opportunity to answer phylogenetic questions by building on this dataset and testing related wild-type or genetically engineered organisms. This approach may provide insights into the impact of genetic modifications on microbial physiology and evolutionary adaptations.

9.2. Genomic Variation

To enable a predictive model capable of designing a microbial genome to process a specific feedstock, future iterations of the dataset will need to utilize the platform to test genomic variations of strains. High-throughput genomics techniques like RB-TnSeq for knockouts and complementation assays for knock-ins may be used^{31,32}. We anticipate that a large dataset of this kind will initially be able to predict gene knock-ins/knockouts that can improve growth in a specific condition. Over time, we hope that these models will eventually be capable of designing complete microbial genomes.

9.3. Additional Measurements

To offer a more comprehensive understanding of microbial responses and adaptations to environmental factors, future iterations can include additional multi-omics measurements. Additional experimental conditions for existing organisms can also be tested to enhance the breadth of the dataset. For instance, growth in the presence of small molecules or industrially relevant inhibitors can be explored.

9.4. Measuring Growth of Microbial Communities

In future iterations of this dataset, we will consider including measurements of microbial communities to study community-level responses to environmental changes and monitor changes in the dominant members of the community. This involves screening for growth under various conditions, with a preliminary focus on growth in the presence of different carbon sources. Samples would be collected from diverse communities with emphasis on sample homogenization, replicate measurement, and testing at various dilution factors.

9.5. Adding New Data Collection Sites

This data collection platform can be implemented across multiple distributed sites without the need for any proprietary technologies. This protocol utilizes commercially available automation equipment commonly found in large laboratories, institutions, and companies. Additionally, many parts of the workflow can be outsourced to service providers; these steps include media preparation, sequencing, and strain onboarding.

The automation capabilities and planned equipment to be used at Align's first two partner sites for this proposal are listed in Table 3, as an example of how this protocol may be executed. However, this can also be performed manually at lower-throughput scales.

Capability	Equipment (Site 1)	Equipment (Site 2)
Spectrophotometry (OD600/UV Vis)	Biotek Epoch 2, Biotek Cytation 5, Biotek Cytation 10	Tecan Spark
Bulk Liquid Handling	Hamilton Nimbus, Opentrons OT2, Biotek Multiflo	Agilent Multiflo
Combinatorial Liquid Handling	ARI Cobra, Formulatrix Mantis, Formulatrix Tempest	Formulatrix Tempest
Microscopy	Biotek Cytation 10	N/A

Table 3: Automation equipment capabilities of data collection partners.

10. Supplemental Material

Supplemental Table 1: Existing Datasets.

Dataset	Paper Title	Year of publication	# of strains	# of conditions	# of growth data points	Data Source
Mori et al. ³³	From coarse to fine: the absolute <i>Escherichia coli</i> proteome under diverse growth conditions	2021	10	60	60	Experimentally generated
Forchielli et al. ³⁴	Metabolic Phenotyping of Marine Heterotrophs on Refactored Media Reveals Diverse Metabolic Adaptations and Lifestyle Strategies	2022	63	10	630	Experimentally generated
Richards et al. (MediaDB) ²³	MediaDB: A Database of Microbial Growth Conditions in Defined Media	2014	208	Not known	765	Manually curated from the DSMZ collection
Ashino et al. ³⁵	Predicting the decision making chemicals used for bacterial growth	2019	1	225	1,336	Experimentally generated
Plata et al. ³⁶	Long-term phenotypic evolution of bacteria	2015	40	62	2,480	Experimentally collected using Biolog plates
Aida et al. ¹³	Machine learning-assisted discovery of growth decision elements by relating bacterial population dynamics to environmental diversity	2022	1	966	12,828	Experimentally generated
Oberhardt et al. (KOMODO) ⁷	Harnessing the landscape of microbial culture media to predict new organism–media pairings	2015	18,049	3,335	20,824	Manually curated
Baranyi and Tamplin (ComBase) ³⁷	ComBase: a common database on microbial responses to food environments	2004	49	Not known	40,000	Manually curated
Koblitz et al. (MediaDive) ²¹	MediaDive: the expert-curated cultivation media database	2023	46,339	3,316	69,373	Manually curated from DSMZ + other sources and publications
Brbić et al. (ProTraits) ³⁸	The landscape of microbial phenotypic traits and associated genes	2016	3,046	424	225,880	Predicted growth traits. No experimental validation
BacDive ⁸	BacDive in 2025: the core database for prokaryotic strain data	2024	97,334	N/A	no quantitative data	Manually curated from DSMZ + other sources and publications

Supplemental Table 2: Media Factors.

Class	Name	Class	Name	Class	Name
Carbon Source	D-(+)-cellobiose	Vitamin Cofactors	4-aminobenzoic acid	Antibacterials/ Antifungals	Gentamicin
	Maltodextrin		D-(+)-Biotin		Ofloxacin
	D-(-)-Fructose		Folic Acid		Penicillin G
	D-(+)-Galactose		Nicotinamide		Oxacillin
	Dextrose (D-Glucose) Anhydrous		D-Pantothenic Acid Hemicalcium		Vancomycin
	D-Mannitol		Pyridoxal Hydrochloride		Sulfamethazine
	D-Lactose Dihydrate		Pyridoxamine Dihydrochloride		Sulfadiazine
	D-Sorbitol		Coenzymell (b-nadph)		Tobramycin
	D-(+)-Trehalose Dihydrate		(-)-Riboflavin		Sulfathiazole
	D-(+)-Mannose		Thiamine Hydrochloride		Rifampicin
	D-Sucrose	Vitamin B12	Guanidine Hydrochloride		
	D-(+)-Raffinose pentahydrate	Nucleobases	adenine		Promethazine
	Melibiose		guanine hydrochloride		Nystatin
	Sodium acetate trihydrate		uracil		Sodium dichromate
	Xylose		cytosine		D-Cycloserine
	Salicin	Metals and Salts	thymine		Triclosan
	Formic Acid		Iron(III) nitrate nonahydrate		3-Amino-1,2,3 triazole
	Arabinose		Potassium Phosphate Dibasic		Miltefosine
	GlcNAc		Calcium Chloride Dihydrate		Polymyxin B
	Oxalic Acid		Sodium Chloride		Azaserine
Propionic Acid	magnesium sulfate heptahydrate		Benzamidine		
Acetic Acid	manganese sulfate monohydrate		Cycloheximide		
Amino Acids	DL-Alanine		zinc chloride	Paromomycin	
	L-Arginine		sodium bicarbonate		
	L-Aspartic Acid		Antibacterials/ Antifungals	fluoride	
	L-Asparagine	hydrogen peroxide			
	L-Cysteine	silver nitrate			
	L-Glutamic Acid	copper sulfate			
	L-Glutamine	tetracycline			
	Glycine	doxycycline			
	L-Histidine	amoxicillin			
	L-Isoleucine	ciprofloxacin			
	L-Leucine	spectinomycin			
	L-Lysine	kanamycin			
	L-Methionine	erythromycin			
	L-Phenylalanine	ampicillin			
	L-Proline	chloramphenicol			
	L-Serine	Fusidic Acid			
	L-Threonine	Puromycin			
	L-Tryptophan	Streptomycin			
	L-Tyrosine	Fusaric Acid			
	L-Valine	Piperacillin			
Other N/P/S Sources	Acetamide	Carbenicillin			
	Formamide	Chlortetracycline			
	Agmatine	Lincomycin			
	Taurine	Bleomycin			
	Thiourea	Colistin			
	Spermidine	Minocycline			
	Butyric Acid	Cefazolin			
	D,L-Carnitine	Neomycin			
	Choline	Ceftriaxone			

11. Suggested Reading

Below is a suggested reading list we recommend for further context:

[“What Biology Can Learn from Physics”, December 2023, Asimov Press.](#)

This proposed dataset platform is part of Align’s Open Dataset Initiative, which pioneers new ways to identify, collect, and share large datasets in life science.

[“BacterAI maps microbial metabolism without prior knowledge”, 2023, Nature Microbiology.](#)

This technique for measuring bacterial growth and using machine learning to select valuable data points was first developed by Paul Jensen’s lab.

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